

Translanguaging as a strategy in English-medium instruction: A retrospective and prospective view

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ABSTRACT

This study is very relevant and useful for the school teachers to make EMI policy successful with the help of the techniques of translanguaging at school level in Nepal. The research objectives of this study attempted to explore retrospective and prospective views of teachers and to find out lived experiences of teachers on the use of translanguaging strategies while implementing EMI in Science, Mathematics and Social Studies Classes. Hermeneutic phenomenological research design was used to explore the lived reflections of secondary level non-English teachers on the use translanguaging strategies in EMI classes. Six teachers of Science, Social Studies and Mathematics subjects were selected as a sample from 3 community schools through judgmental non-random sampling method in this study. The results of this study revealed that teachers and learners have been using different translanguaging strategies in EMI classes such as L1 as a source of learning strategy, dual modes of medium of instruction, translation, code mixing, and code switching in EMI classes, and ICT as a strategy in EMI classes. Furthermore, it was found that there was lack of instructional materials to support EMI policies in community schools. Translanguaging has been adopted by the Science, Social Studies and Mathematics teachers to make EMI policy of Government of Nepal successful and effective in community schools. The educational authorities of Local Government should organize workshop, seminar and short-term workshop and training on the techniques of translanguaging to implement the decision of English as a Medium of instruction in community schools in Nepal.

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INTRODUCTION

Nepali language has been using as a first language or a mother tongue by 46.23% of the total population of Nepal whereas 53.77% of people use their own mother tongues beside Nepali language (NPHC, 2021). According to NPHC (2021), 124 national languages are spoken in different environmental areas in Nepal. Moreover, Maithili is spoken by 0.92%, Hindi by 0.76%, Bhojपुरi by 0.48%, English by 0.35%, Tharu by 0.31%, Bajjika by 0.30%, Avadhi by 0.26%, Urdu by 0.25%, Tamang by 0.25%, Magar Dhut by 0.19%, Bhoti by 0.16%, Bantawa by 0.15%, Newari by 0.11%, Chamling by 0.10%, Magahi by 0.10%, Gurung by 0.08%, Limbu by 0.07%, Thulung by 0.06%, Magar Kham by 0.06%, Bahing by 0.05%, Rai by 0.05%, Doteli by 0.05%, Sampang by 0.05%, Khaling by 0.04%, Baitadeli by 0.03%, Sherpa by 0.03%, Sanskrit by 0.02%, Achhami by 0.02%, Angika by 0.02%, Musalman by 0.02%, Kulung by 0.02%, Dumi by 0.02%, Dadeldhuri by 0.02%, Bangla by 0.02%, and Wambule by 0.02%, in Nepal (NPHC, 2021).

Nepal is a home for a variety of social, cultural, religious, linguistic and ethnic groups. One hundred and twenty-four languages are acknowledged as national languages as per census of 2021. There are 142 official caste and ethnic groups, each of which practices 10 different religious systems viz. Hinduism, Buddhism, Islam, Kirat, Christianity, Prakriti, Bon, Jainism, Bahai and Sikhism (NPHC, 2021). Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) has become failure in the Nepali context since the learners have developed the concepts and philosophy of teaching target language using their L1 as translanguaging strategies so using only target language in the EFL context like Nepal cannot be effective. The classroom of English language teaching (ELT) comprises of diverse learners in terms of different languages and cultures. Furthermore, The languages are vehicles of promoting national unity and integrity in diverse country like Nepal. The national languages are the main means of developing harmony to one another at local, provincial, national and global levels (Awasthi, 2011). EMI has been regarded as a buzz globalized trend in the 21st century. Moreover, English is thought to be a visa card to get entry in the global village (Kadel, 2024). Furthermore, there is increasing the scope and inevitability of English in the field of higher education, employment, travelling, and even better life. Every parent and guardian demands to implement EMI from pre-school to secondary level with school management committee and school administration instead of mother tongue based multilingual education (MTB-MLE); however, National Curriculum Framework for school education (2019) stated that medium of instruction up to grade three can be children's local mother tongues. There is a controversy and conflict between the perspectives of the parents, guardians and incumbent policy makers of Government of Nepal in this regard.

Nepali language policy, planning and practices can be categorized into four periods: Rana Oligarchy period, Panchayat Period, Democracy Period, and Federal Republic Period (Awasthi, 2004, 2011; Giri, 2011; Phyak, 2011; Weinberg, 2013). The Rana Oligarchy period which started from 1856 and ended 1950 was known as opposite of education. At that time, only one school, Durbar High School was established only for the children of Royal family, Rana, courtiers, and a few of elites; however, it was open for public citizens in 1902. Nepali language was the main official and medium of instruction in Rana Oligarchy period and Panchayat period. However, the establishment of Durbar High School in 1854 was marked the beginning of English education in school level in Nepal. Formally, English education in school level began in Nepal since 1854. More importantly, the entry of English education in higher education began with the foundation of Tri-Chandra college in 1918. The introduction of English language teaching and learning was confined only for the children of Rana family, and courtiers which was unscientific, impractical and autocratic policies of Rana Oligarch. If English language education was proliferated across the country for common people during Rana Oligarchy, people of Nepal would be much more advanced, cultured, witty, and civilized with the help of English language education.

English language teaching at school and higher education started since 1971 with the introduction of National Education System Plan (NESP) in Nepal (Awasthi, 2019). The policy of EMI was shifted to Nepali as a medium of instruction when there was the collapse of the Rana Regime in 1950. The continuation of English language education would help to flourish English language education in the 21st century in Nepal; however, there was discontinuation of English education after the downfall of Rana Oligarchy. During the Panchayat system from 1960 to 1990, there

was Nepali as a Medium of Instruction (NMI) mode of instruction which weakened the vernacular languages as well as EMI in Nepal.

The policy of EMI was restored in Nepal after the collapse of the Monarchy in 2006 (Kadel, 2024). However, the main reasons behind the shifting to EMI from NMI were the impact of globalisation, English as a globalized language, neo-liberalisation and an open marketing system in Nepal. The culture of language use in education has been critically analysed and interpreted through of socio-political, historical, and economic approaches (Poudel, 2019). All of the languages spoken as mother tongues were declared as national languages in the Constitution of Kingdom of Nepal in 1990. The federal republic period started from 2007 to onwards has incorporated the neoliberal language ideology to preserve and promote the mother tongues of 142 ethnic groups in Nepal. This period has become a golden age for EMI because Government of Nepal decided to implement EMI mode of instruction in community schools; however, there was EMI mode of instruction in institutional schools (private schools) in Nepal since 1990.

There was mushrooming of private schools known as institutional schools particularly in urban city areas across the country. EMI and MTB-MLE have been enacted in school level. EMI has been implemented in most of community schools when school sector development plan (SSDP: 2016-2023) was enacted in school education. The SSDP (2016-2023) has set up MTB-MLE language policy with the association of the notions of equality, equity and inclusion (Brown, 2018, p. 26). The trilingual policy of using Nepali, English and provincial languages was implemented in 2007. According to School Sector Reform Plan (SSRP) report (2009-2015) of bilingual policy of using NMI and EMI has been laid out across the country. The medium of instruction can be either Nepali or English or both (National Curriculum Framework, 2007). Moreover, the selection of EMI at school level can be decided by the school management committee in the consultation with the local government (SSRP, 2007-2015).

Translanguaging (TL) is a useful learning strategy for the ESL and EFL learners since it evokes the learners with their linguistic repertoire and previous experiences (Graham et al., 2021). More importantly, TL helps the learners to collect more knowledge about the subject which they have been dealing with. The identities of the learners have been incorporated and highlighted through TL strategy in the class thereby encouraging them more participation in their learning (Rosiers et al., 2018). In fact, EFL and ESL learners can utilize multilingual resources in the meaning making process (Wei, 2018) so that they can develop their critical thinking skills through the use of TL practices in the class. TL is against the monolingual and conventional ideologies in which learners' inadequate monolingual linguistic repertoire has been used in course of meaning making process (Tai & Wong, 2022). TL pedagogy is a macro and broader approach in which ESL and EFL learners' linguistic and cultural repertoire and background knowledge of their L1 are used to make meaning in course of the practices of policy of EMI (Wei, 2023). Translanguaging pedagogy is essential in diverse classroom for consolidating inclusion and social justice. However, pedagogical translanguaging is regarded as translanguaging practice as a tool for teaching and learning by using learners' home language as a source of knowledge to understand ambiguous issues in Science, Social Studies and Mathematics classes. In addition, translanguaging activates the learners to move across their languages including linguistics repertoires in writing and record their stories. Translanguaging pedagogy tries to incorporate a variety of languages and diverse cultures to construct personal and institutional identities (Sato, 2023). The main focus of translanguaging is the strategic integration of languages in the EMI class. TL is to be helpful and supportive for the lower proficient learners of English (Burton & Rajendram, 2019).

Students would develop a sense of security and comfort while expressing their thoughts, feelings and ideas through their L1 to construct meaning in EMI mode of pedagogical classes (Thongwichit & Ulla, 2024). Translanguaging pedagogy is considered as a form of scaffolding means of connecting students' L1 repertoire with the content in EMI classes. Translanguaging is an alternative pedagogical strategy that permits to use both L1 of the learners and English as target language to find out the resources to comprehend the content (Chaka, 2024; Motaung, 2024). Translanguaging strategy creates a lively conducive environment to enhance learning. The learners can be benefitted through translanguaging strategy in non-English subjects such as Science, Mathematics and Social Studies. More importantly, translanguaging helps the learners enhance their communicative competence and classroom

participation (Tumansery & Munden, 2020). The learners can develop content knowledge and linguistic repertoire through the L1 resources thereby developing a positive impact on students' learning.

Nepali language has been using as an official and day to day language in the government offices and medium of instruction in school education since the inception of Durbar High School in Nepal. However, EMI was executed as a medium of teaching and learning in community schools after the introduction of Federal Democratic Republic county of Nepal. Nepali and English as medium of instructions in the community schools are the two existing modes of instruction in community schools. In this regard, Sah and Li (2022) argue that EMI and NMI were only used in the EMI class; however, the learner's L1 resources were excluded from the EMI classes. The exclusion of learners' prior linguistic recourses invites a serious problem in EMI classes. Likewise, Sharma (2022) carried out an empirical study on translanguaging as a mediator of learning in which he concluded that there are a plenty of advantages of using translanguaging in EMI classes. More importantly, Sharma (2022) asserts that that translanguaging can be used as a mediated strategy for cognitive, affective and interactional dimension in English language instruction. Due to the low English competency of learners, they cannot comprehend the knowledge of subject matter of Mathematic, social studies and Science. Moreover, the teachers of Mathematics and Science could not communicate contents of their subject through simple English owing to the low proficiency over English in the Kathmandu metropolitan city where there is a majority of Newar community people whose L1 is Newari language so this study would be very relevant to support the EMI policy of Government of Nepal.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

The objectives of this study were as follows:

- To explore in-depth retrospective and prospective experiences of Science, Mathematics and Social Studies teachers while implementing EMI at school level;
- To investigate the lived reflections of teachers on the use of translanguaging strategies while employing EMI in Science, Mathematics and social studies Classes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Design

The main reason behind selecting hermeneutic phenomenological research design rather than other research designs such as narrative inquiry, case study, and ethnography research designs under qualitative research approach was to explore the in-depth lived experiences and reflections of the participants. This research design was very adequate to delve personal cognitive experiences of teachers regarding the appropriate translanguaging strategies in EMI classes to make the learners understand content knowledge as well as to develop competency in English language simultaneously. The hermeneutic phenomenological research design was used to delve subjective and multiple realities (Campbell, 2015) of the teachers on translanguaging as a strategy in EMI classes. This research design tries to explore the comprehending meaning and importance of lived reflections of the participants regarding the use of translanguaging in EMI classes (Diaz, 2015). Phenomenology is regarded as "social and cultural situatedness of actions and interactions, together with participants' interpretation of actions" (Cohen, et al., 2018, p. 21). Hermeneutical phenomenology is constructivist approach that admits the existence of multiple socially constructed realities (Hatch, 2002). The hermeneutical phenomenological research was used to elicit and interpret the data that "aims to describe phenomena as they are lived and experienced by participants and as they are described by them" (Riazi, 2016a, p. 45).

Participants of the Study

There were 6 teachers of Science, Mathematics and Social Studies from three community schools of Kathmandu district as participants who were selected through judgmental non-random sampling method.

Research Instruments

The semi-structure in-depth-interview was employed to the participants to elicit the lived reflection. In addition, classroom observation was used as a tool to elicit data regarding the use translanguaging as techniques in EMI class to address the research objectives in this study. The field note was used while conducting classroom observation.

Research Site

The selected schools were entitled as School A, School B, and School C to maintain confidentiality and anonymity.

Data Analysis

The data were collected physically. Subsequently, the collected data were translated into English from Nepali, Newari, Tamang and local languages shared by the participants shared in their local vernacular languages. The organized themes were evolved out of the basic themes. Even the basic themes were developed out of codes and decodes. Finally, 5 main themes were evolved out of organized themes. The global themes were manually based on the basic and organized themes. NVivo software could be used to develop themes through the coded and decoded data; however, this software was not used to develop global themes in this study. The data were analysed and interpreted thematically by inserting the remarkable verbatim of the participants while interpreting the data. Interpretive research paradigm was used to analyse and interpret the data collected from participants.

Ethical Consideration

The pseudonyms were used for each participant to maintain anonymity and confidentiality of the participants in this study. The participants as pseudonyms were Hari, Shyam, Prachanda, Kiran, Gita, and Krishna who voluntarily provided data despite being busy in their own business. All of the participants were behaved frankly and democratic manner in course of administering interview. First and foremost, head teachers of 3 schools were requested to grant the permission to collect data in their schools. The information was elicited by administering in-depth interview and conducting classroom observation. The consents of subject teachers were permitted by the subject teachers to conduct the classroom observation. It was very feasible to triangulate data collected through in-depth-semi-structured interview and conducting classroom observation. The transcribed data were sent to the participants to confirm their data provided during the semi-structured in-depth interview. The member check strategy (Cohen et al., 2018) was used to confirm their information in this study.

Since it is qualitative research, there was no any numerical data. In order to maintain data integrity, I asked to each participant to check their transcribed data physically to maintain data validation because the participants were available. Three community secondary schools located in Kirtipur Municipality of Kathmandu district were selected as sample schools using judgmental non-random sampling method. The Community schools A, B, and C were selected because EMI program has been implemented since 2006 in these community schools. Furthermore, six participants at least 2 participants from each secondary school were selected using judgmental non-random sampling method in this study. The participants pseudonyms as Hari, Shyam, Prachanda, Kiran, Gita, and Krishna were chosen because they have been teaching in EMI school since 2018.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, 5 global themes viz. L1 as a learning strategy, dual mode of medium of instruction, translation, code switching, and code mixing in EMI Class, and ICT as a strategy in EMI class, and Lack of instructional materials in schools were developed on the basis of organized and basic themes provided by the participants in course of data collection using in-depth semi-structured interview and classroom observation.

L1 as a Learning Strategy

Nepal is a multilingual and multiethnic country situated between two giant countries China and India. There are 124 national languages and 142 ethnic groups (NPHC, 2021) in this tiny country so classroom is a miniature. In this context, one of the participants, Hari argued that “English is regarded as a foreign language in Nepal. The parents of each learner do not use English in their home so the learners have very poor English proficiency. Even the medium of instruction from pre-school to grade 3 is not English. The learners are provided basic education from pre-school to grade 3 through either NMI or MTB-MLE so their foundation of English proficiency is very poor”.

If the learners are encouraged to share their L1 linguistic repertoire when they feel difficulty to comprehend the contents of different subjects such as Science, Social studies, and Mathematic in EMI classes, they can easily internalize the concepts of content knowledge through their L1 lens. In this regard, L1 is a useful learning strategy for the ESL and EFL learners since it evokes the learners with their linguistic repertoire and previous experiences (Graham et al., 2021). The difficult terminology in EMI classes can be understood through the use of L1 resources. Moreover, there are multilingual learners in the class. They can have discussion and interaction by dividing them into small groups in terms of heterogeneous and homogeneous language groups. The participants, Shyam, Prachanda, Kiran, Gita, Surya and Krishna also agreed that L1 resources are very essential and useful tool to understand Science, Social Studies and Mathematic in EMI classes. In a similar vein, Prachanda asserted that “Learners’ L1 repertoire plays a significant role in my science class to make understand the whole class so L1 resources are to be applied to other classes like Geography, Algebra, Arithmetic, Geometry etc. The learners can analyse the meaning and concept delivered in English language through the repertoire of their home language in Mathematics and Science classes.”

Mother tongue based multilingual education from pre-primary to grade 3 is very relevant and essential to develop the basic schema of learners about the world around them. So, MTB-MLE program can be complementary for EMI program implemented in community schools in Nepal from 2006. In this point, Krishna claimed that “the learners even shared the difficult concepts in Social studies class with their peers who are from different language communities to construct meaning in their L1”. It can be inferred that the home language of the learners become a reliable tool for meaning making process in Mathematics, Science, and Social Studies EMI classes. In this regard, Kiran stated that multilingual classroom can be source of resources of knowledge and skills in different subjects; however, the teaching and learning should be restricted on the learner-centred digital pedagogy. If the learners get opportunities to share their ideas and knowledge in each subject through English language in the classroom, they can develop their critical thinking skills and problem-solving skills.

Nepal is a diverse country with students from different communities in terms of language, culture, and religion. There are much resources in the classroom due to the heterogeneous students from various language communities.

Dual Modes of Medium of Instruction

Nepal was ruled by Monarchs for more than 240 years. There was dominance of Nepali as a medium of instruction (NMI) from the Rana Oligarchy period to Democracy Period in Nepal till 2006. Before federal democratic republic age, there was one language one nation policy in which medium of instruction in community schools was NMI. In this regard, the participant, Kiran argued that “English as a medium of instruction began in community schools after the rooted out of the Monarchy in 2006 and dawn of federal democratic republic system in Nepal. Even after implementing EMI formally in community schools, there is no EMI in non-English subjects such as Science, Mathematics and Social Studies. Every subject were taught adopting NMI in community schools”. However, parents and guardians are pressurizing the school management committee and headteacher to execute EMI strictly in community schools.

Due to the low competency in English of both teachers and learners, it is very difficult to implement EMI in community schools because most of the students in community schools are from poor English backgrounds. Translanguaging as a technique help the non-Nepali speakers to comprehend the content knowledge as such, they can get good grade in the examination. NMI is adopted even by the teachers of Science, Mathematics and Social studies in community schools. The participants Shyam, Prachanda, Krishna, Kiran and Gita also agreed in this regard. In this point, the participant, Gita asserted that “when I start teaching adopting EMI in my Science class, the students ask me to share in Nepal language for the learners whose mother tongue is Nepali. Likewise, the learners from Newari language community ask me to share the concept, and meaning of terminology in Newari language since the classroom is multilingual”. Translanguaging is used to make the learners understand the concepts of particular subject matters in English by connecting students’ L1 repertoire in EMI classes. Translanguaging as a strategy has been used in EMI classes in community schools in Nepal. All of the participants accepted the translanguaging as a strategy in EMI classes. The main cause of shifting from Nepali as a Medium of Instruction (NMI) to EMI is the impact of globalisation, English as lingua franca, neo-liberalisation and open marketing system in Nepal.

Translation, Code Switching and Code Mixing in EMI Class

The teachers of Science, Social Studies and Mathematics follow the various strategies to make the EMI campaigns successful in community schools. Without adopting various techniques such as translation, code mixing and code switching in EMI class, EMI policy of Government of Nepal cannot be implemented in community schools. In this regard, Krishna stated that “teachers translate the content knowledge into the mother tongues of the learners by the help of the students themselves. If there is no translation of content into the L1 of the learners, EMI cannot be effective and implemented in the community schools”.

Grammar translation as a method of teaching has become very popular and effective in the Nepalese history of ELT since 1940s in the context of Nepal. In a similar vein, the code switching and code mixing are the popular translanguaging techniques in the EMI classes. There is fusion of learners’ home languages and English in Science, Social Studies and Mathematics classes. Another participant, Gita argued that “there is overlapping of NMI and EMI in Science, Social Studies and Mathematics classes. The teachers of Science and Mathematics adopt the techniques of mixing more than two languages and shifting into more than two languages in EMI science, social studies and mathematics classes which becomes very effective and productive for the learners”.

Code switching and code mixing are adopted as translanguaging strategies to run EMI in Science Social Studies and Mathematics classes in community schools. NMI and EMI are fusion and overlapping together in non-English subject’s classes since the learners are from poor background of English. They cannot understand terminology and jargons of each subject without translating them into their mother tongues. If the teachers use only English, the low proficient English learners cannot comprehend the subject matter knowledge delivered in English. In this regard, the teacher should use the technique of changing language from English to Nepali and other mother tongues of the learners. Moreover, L1 is a useful learning strategy for the ESL and EFL learners since it evokes the leaners with their L1 linguistic repertoires (Graham et al., 2021). In this context, the participant Shyam argued that “owing to poor communicative competence of learners in English, they use their L1 in course of communicating in English in sscience with EMI lead Classes. The classes of non-English subjects in community schools are extremely diverse in terms of languages and ethnic groups so changing from English to Nepali, Newari, Tamang, and Tharu languages and vice versa are common features in non-English subjects in EMI classes”.

In this point, all of the participants Hari, Kiran, Gita, Prachanda, and Krishna agreed that the learners implement code mixing, code switching and translation techniques and strategies in the EMI classes of Science, Social Studies and Mathematics to catch up the content knowledge due to the poor English competency of the learners. It is very challenging to implement EMI in community schools without adopting mixing of two languages and changing from one language to another language in EMI classes as well as translation as strategies. The teachers are to be provided proper workshop and training to support EMI policy of Government of Nepal.

ICT as a Strategy in EMI Class

Information Communication Technology (ICT) based learning in science education provides active learning, enables students to perform with higher order thinking skills, supports for constructive learning and promotes scientific inquiry and conceptual change (Jimoyiannis, 2010). The teachers and learners need to develop their ICT skills to use in the EMI classroom in order to increase the learning capacity of the learners (Srisawasdi, 2012). Moreover, if the teachers have sound ICT expertise, they can collect instructional materials from free e-library for the learners and themselves. In this regard, Kiran stated that “the learners’ comprehensive skills in English can be developed by giving comprehensive passage on content knowledge with questions using Edu-puzzle and padlet which are the tools of ICT”. The classroom should be equipped with smartboard and free internet access so that learners can use ICT freely in classroom. ICT is one of the 21st century skills to facilitate EMI policy.

ICT skills are required for innovation in the learning. Digital competency includes information management collaboration, communication and sharing, creation of content knowledge ethics and responsibilities evaluation and problem solving and technical operation (Ferrari, 2012). In the EMI classes, if the teachers and learners are equipped with ICT skills and knowledge, they can share the webinar videos, and podcast videos on the content knowledge of each subject through English language. In this point, Prachanda stated that “the classroom should be modernized and digitalized with smartboard with free internet access in the class. Moreover, the learners should be allowed to bring their laptops and smart mobile phones in the class so that they can search content knowledge in the class”.

The learners can learn life skills through the use of literacy digital skills which includes information, media and ICT literacy. The teachers and learners can have dialogues through the public media using English language regarding the problems in Social Studies, Mathematics and Science with their peers and tutors as well. They can have group interaction and discussion regarding the EMI and content materials through the use of public media like vibre, WhatsApp, Facebook etc.

Lack of Instructional Materials in School

There is a lack of instructional materials to support the EMI policy of Government of Nepal. If the learners and teachers are provided with adequate instructional materials with free of cost, they can develop the culture of reading of their specific learning materials. In this regard, the participant, Prachanda asserted that “there is no e-library in my school to prepare the instructional materials in English. Most of outdated reference books and textbooks are available in the physical library in Nepali language. It is very difficult for us to translate the terminology and jargons into standard English language. If there is open access of e-library provided by the school administration, we can download the materials and shared to the learners and we can also share the link of the sources to them. I personally cannot afford the sources by subscribing money to read the materials”.

The school administration should establish the e-library and internet access for teachers and learners by subscribing the sources. The reading culture of teachers and learners has been deteriorating day by day due to the lack of latest fresh updated materials. Majority of participants accepted that there is a lack of e-instructional materials owing to the shortage of internet access and e-library in community schools.

DISCUSSION

There has been learning achievement of Science, Mathematics, Social Studies, and English due to the use of translanguaging as techniques in EMI classes. In this regard, Sah and Li argued (2022) that the students whose mother tongues are not Nepali language were very much benefited and facilitated by the use of translanguaging in English as a Medium of instruction. Based on the data of the participants’, translanguaging policy has become a remarkable local pedagogical policy in Nepal. Using translanguaging in the EMI classes of English, Science, and Mathematics, non-Nepali speakers can understand the content knowledge well. The learners can use the subject matter knowledge to address the questions in the final examination of each subject smartly. Based on the responses of each participant, there is increasement of learning achievement using translanguaging techniques in the EMI classes in school level in Nepal. One of the results of this study is that L1 as a learning strategy to facilitate the

learners to employ EMI in Science, Social Studies and Mathematics classes. The resources of L1 are very useful to understand the contents taught in English language of non-English subjects in EMI classes. The learners' home language or L1 facilitates them to comprehend Science, social Studies and Mathematics taught using EMI effectively. The use of L1 of the learners help to comprehend the contents in the Mathematics, Science and Social Studies (Chaka, 2024; Motaung, 2024).

L1 and L2 seem to exist separately at the surface level; however, at the core level, L1 and L2 languages are processed through common underlying proficiency (Cummins, 1980, 1981) so, knowledge understood in L1 can be transferred into L2, and L3 easily. The use of dual modes like NMI and EMI have been applied to mitigate the problems arise in EMI classes of Science, Social Studies and Mathematics at secondary levels. Translanguaging is a strategy that permits the learners to use both L1 of the learners and target language to find out the resources to comprehend the content (Chaka, 2024; Motaung, 2024) in Science and Mathematics classes. The learners and teachers of Science, Social Studies and Mathematics have been using language mixing, language changing and translation as translanguaging strategies to make the success of the policy of EMI of Government of Nepal. The strategies of language mixing, language changing and translation have been proved as milestones in EMI classes. More importantly, teaching of Science, Social Studies and Mathematics through EMI cannot be successful and effective without integrating ICT in each subject. At this point of 21st century. ICT has become a rudimentary and complementary strategy to teach any subject in EMI classes. It is observed that ICT has become a backbone in the school curricula. In order to make the learners and teachers competent and proficient in English, there should be sufficient teaching and reading material in the e-library. However, it was found the shortage of teaching and learning e-materials in each school. There are no fresh and the latest teaching and learning materials in the school library. Moreover, there are a lack of e-library and e-book corner in each sampled schools in this study.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIOS

English as a medium of instruction is a burning issue in community schools in Nepal. Due to the excessive use of English in every sphere in Nepal, English has been acknowledged as a key to get entry of careers in the field of education, ICT, business, politics, diplomacy, and foreign employment. In this regard, EMI has become a buzz word in education so, every guardian and parent pressurize the school management committee to implement EMI in community schools. In order to execute EMI in Science, Mathematics, and Social Studies, the findings of this study would be very actionable and contributory for teachers and students in school level. Furthermore, the strategies of translanguaging such as L1 as a learning strategy, translation, language mixing, language switching and ICT as strategies in EMI classes would be the milestone to make the EMI policy in non-English subjects in the school level.

The responsibilities of school education systems are under the Local Government in Nepal as per the Constitution of Nepal (2015) so, there should be reciprocal agreement between provincial universities and Local Governmental bodies to support the teachers of school level by conducting workshop, seminar, webinar and training on strategies of tanslanguaging in EMI classes. The authorities of Local Government should have tripartite agreements among authorities of universities of provincial leaderships, school level authorities and local authorities regarding the training of ICT to the teachers to make strategies of translanguaging in EMI workshops and trainings for teacher professional development. Moreover, the Local Government should hire the mentors from provincial and federal universities to train the school teachers and conduct the workshop and training to implement EMI in every subject in school level. The federal government should allocate considerable amount of budget to revamp the teaching methods and techniques as well as existing EMI system. There should be radical changes of traditional method of chalk and talk method of teaching into digitalized pedagogy. The digital pedagogy must be implemented in school education to bring remarkable changes in the medium of instruction in school level education. The school management committee should invest huge amount of money to digitalize every classroom to implement EMI effectively. Every class should be equipped with smartboards, podiums and desktop computers for the students and teachers. There should be internet access in every class in the community schools. The parents and teachers should avoid the misconceptions from their minds that the students would spoil their careers by using computers and internet because this is the age of 21st century.

The researcher felt very hardship to administer in-depth interview with the teachers. He spent hours to get appointment with the participants to administer interview. However, he was successful to collect data through in-depth semi-structured interview with non-English subject teachers. The participants felt very uncomfortable to conduct their classroom observation. The researcher was successful to observe classes of only four teachers. However, two teachers did not allow him to conduct their classroom observation. The finding of this research could not be absolutely panacea. The further research can be conducted entitled “Challenges and Potentialities of using translanguaging techniques in EMI classes at Basic Level in Nepal: Perceptions of Students and Parents”.

REFERENCES

- Awasthi, J. R. (2019). *Trajectories of ELT and Applied Linguistics in Nepal: Twists, turns and way forward*. A paper presented at second ELT and Applied Linguistics Conference organized by the Department of English Education in 2019, Tribhuvan University, Nepal.
- Awasthi, L. D. (2004). *Exploring the monolingual school practices in multilingual Nepal*. University of education dissertation.
- Awasthi, L. D. (2011). Importation of ideologies: From Macaulay to Wood commission report. In L. Farrell, U. N. Singh & R. A. Giri (Eds.), *English language education in South Asia: From policy to pedagogy* (pp. 73-88). Cambridge University Press.
- Awasthi, L. D. (2011). The making of Nepal’s language policy: Importation of ideologies. In L. Farrell, U. N. Singh & R.A. Giri (Eds.), *English language education in South Asia* (pp. 73-88). Foundation Books.
- Awasthi, L. D. (2019). The making of Nepal’s language policy: Importation of ideologies. In L. Farrell, U. N. Singh & R. A. Giri (Eds.), *English language education in south Asia*. (pp. 73-88). Foundation Books.
- Brown, R. (2018). English and its roles in education: Subject or medium of instruction? In D. Hayes (Ed.) *English language teaching in Nepal: Research, reflection and practice*. British Council.
- Burton, J. & Rajendram, S. (2019). Translanguaging-as-resource: university ESL instructors’ language orientations and attitudes towards languaging. *TESL Canada Journal*, 36(1), 21-47. <https://doi.org/10.18806/tesl.V36I1.1301>
- Campbell, T. A. (2015). A phenomenological study on international doctoral students’ acculturating experiences at a US university. *Journal of International Students*, 5(3), 285-299.
- Chaka, C., (2024). Multilingualism translanguaging, diversity, equity, social justice and activities: A tenuous nexus and misrepresentations. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(1), 7-28.
- Cohen, L. Manion, L. & Morrison, K. (2018). *Research methods in education*. Tylor and Francis.
- Constitution of Nepal (2015). *Constitution of Nepal*. Government of Nepal.
- Cummins, J. (1980). The cross-lingual dimensions of language proficiency: Implications for bilingual education and the optimal age issue: *TESOL Quarterly*, 14(2), 174-187.
- Cummins, J. (1981). Empirical and theoretical underpinnings of bilingual education. *Journal of Education*, 163(1), 16-29.
- Diaz, A. R. & Moore, P J. (2024). (Re) imagining a course in intercultural communication for the 21st century. *Intercultural Communication Education*, 1 (3), 84—99.
- Diaz. M. P. (2015). Phenomenology in educational qualitative research: Philosophy as science or philosophical science? *International Journal of Educational Excellence*, 1(2), 101-110.
- Giri, R. A. (2011). Language and languages politics: How invisible language politics produces visible results in Nepal. *Language Problems and Language Planning*, 35, (3), 197-221.
- Graham, K., Eslami, Z., & Hillman, S. (2021). From English as the medium to English as a medium: Perspectives of EMI students in Qatar. *System*, 99, 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2021.102508>
- Hatch, J. A. (2002). *Doing qualitative research in education settings*. State university of New York Press.
- Jimoyiannis, A. (2010). Designing and implementing an integrated technological pedagogical science knowledge framework for science teacher professional development. *Computer & Education*, 55, 1259-1269.
- Kadel, P. B. (2024). Potentialities and challenges of adopting English as a medium of instruction at basic level in Nepal. Pragyaratna. <https://doi.org/10.3126/pragyaratna.v6i2.70591>

- Motaung, L. B. (2024). Translanguaging pedagogical practice in a tutorial programme at a South African university. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(1), 81-104.
- National Curriculum Framework (2007). *Government of Nepal. Ministry of Education*. Curriculum Development Centre.
- National Curriculum Framework for School Education (2019). *Government of Nepal, Ministry of Education, Science, and Technology*. Curriculum Development Centre.
- National Education Policy (2019). National education policy. *Ministry of Education, Science and Technology*, Government of Nepal: Kathmandu.
- NPHC (2021). *National population and housing census*. Government of Nepal, Office of the Prime Minister and Council of Ministers, National Statistics Office.
- Phyak, P. B. (2011). Beyond the façade of language planning for Nepalese primary education: Monolingual hangover, elitism and displacement of local language? *Current Issues in Language Planning*, 12(2). 265-287.
- Poudel, P. P. (2019). The medium of instruction policy in Nepal: Towards critical engagement on the ideological and pedagogical debate. *Journal of Language and Education*, 5(3), 102-110. <http://doi.org/10.17323/jle.2019.8995>.
- Riazi, A. M. (2016a). Innovative mixed-methods research: Moving beyond design technicalities to epistemological and methodological realizations. *Applied Linguistics*, 37(1), 33-49.
- Rosiers, K., Lancker, L., & Delarue, S. (2018). Beyond the tradition scope of translanguaging: Comparing translanguaging practices in Belgian multilingual and monolingual classroom contexts. *Language and Communication*, 61, 15-28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.langcom.2017.11.003>
- Sah, P. K. & Li, G. (2022). Translanguaging or unequal languaging? Unfolding the plurilingual discourse of English medium instruction policy in Nepal in public schools. *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*. 25(6), 2075-2094. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13670050.2020.1849011>
- Sato, R. (2023). Japanese EFL speakers' willingness to communicate in L2 conversation: The effect of code-switching and translanguaging. *TESL-EJ*, 27(3), 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.55593/ej.27107a5>
- School Sector Reform Plan (SSRP) (2009-2015). Government of Nepal. Ministry of Education, Science and Technology.
- Sharma, U. N. (2022). Translanguaging as a mediator of learning: Observation in the ELT classes of Nepal. *Education and Development*, 32(1), 105-120. <https://doi.org/10.3126/ed.v32i1.61586>
- Srisawasdi, N. (2012). The role of TPACK in physics classroom: Case studies of preservice physics teachers. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 46, 3235-3243. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.06.043>
- Tai, K. /W. & Wong, C. (2022). Empowering students through the construction of a translanguaging space in an English as a first language classroom. *Applied Linguistics*, <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781848607927>
- Thongwichit, N. & Ulla, M. B. (2024). Translanguaging pedagogy in Thailand's English medium of instruction classrooms: Teachers' perspectives and practices. *TESL-EJ*, 27 (4). <https://doi.org/10.55593/ej.27108a7>
- Tulmansery, G. S. & Munden, J. (2020). Communicative competence in English upper secondary school curriculum in Indonesia, *International Journal of Language Studies*, 14(3). 1-26.
- Wei, L. (2018). Translanguaging as a practical theory of language. *Applied Linguistics*, 39, (1), 9-30.
- Wei, L. (2023). Transformative pedagogy for inclusion and social justice through translanguaging, co-learning, and transpositioning. *Language Teaching*, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0261444823000186>
- Weinberg, M. (2013). Revisiting history in language policy: The case of medium of instruction in Nepal. *Penn Libraries*, 28 (1). Retrieved from <http://repository>. Upenn.edu/wpel/vol.28.